

Positive Deviance and Early Life Nutrition Based on Local Wisdom for Pregnant Women with the Nutritional Status of Children Aged 0-5 Years with Covid-19 Case

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ABSTRACT

The significant role of a mother is primarily evident from the birth of her baby. So that the pattern of nutritional intake of pregnant women can be in line with health standards. A mother who is pregnant in a household that is also part of the family is no longer an adult, but a mother must be seen as a complete and unique individual whom she has a dual role in terms of nutritional intake at the time of her pregnancy. A mother has special and greater needs that are different from the ones of ordinary adults. An adequate and balanced intake of nutritional needs is very important for the pregnancy to prevent iron deficiency and essential fatty acids in newborn infants and toddlers. The pattern of nutritional intake plays an important role in providing standard nutritional intake (Needs: Carbohydrates, Proteins, Vitamins, Minerals, Fats). Coronavirus diseases 2019 or what we usually short for covid-19 is now a problem in Indonesia and even in the world, especially after death cases in a short time. Knowledge about outbreaks and health protocol rules on adapting normal habits in the community is still very lacking. Corona Virus Disease 2019 is a type of virus identified as the cause of disease in the respiratory tract. Transmission of Corona Virus Disease 2019 or Covid-19 still occurs over the globe. The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends the program to reduce the incidence of Covid-19 transmission. The main causes of death in children under five years during pregnancy in developing countries, based on the death related to malnutrition by 35%, namely

pneumonia 20%, diarrhoea 15%, dengue 11%, perinatal 23%, other 22%, measles 5% and HIV/AIDS 4%. The research carried out in Baregbeg Village, Baregbeg District, Ciamis Regency in 2022.

INTRODUCTION

Corona virus diseases 2019 or what we usually call covid-19 is currently a problem in Indonesia and even in the world. This can bring new changes to the social order of Indonesian people's lives. The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends programs to reduce the case rate of Covid-19 transmission (1). The importance of a mother's role is primarily evident from the birth of her child (2). In order that the pattern of nutritional intake of pregnant women to be in accordance with health standards, besides having to manage the right diet, it is also important to regulate the right parenting as well (3). The right parenting can be done by giving full attention and affection to the child and giving enough time to the child to enjoy togetherness with all family members (4). Nutritional intake patterns play an important role in providing nutritional intake standards (Needs: Carbohydrates, Proteins, Vitamins, Minerals, Fats) that have nutritional values and standards to become balanced nutrition that can change behaviour and provide a source of motivation for mothers to fulfil nutritional intake that can be a source of the health for pregnant women (2) (5).

The main cause of the death of children under five, during the pregnancy, in developing countries, deal with malnutrition is 35%, pneumonia is 20%, diarrhea is 15%, malaria is 11%, perinatal is 23%, other is 22%, meals is 5% and HIV/AIDS. Mother's behavior regarding parenting pattern, feeding pattern, hygiene pattern and habit of bringing to health services and early life nutrition are expected to overcome bad behavior such as letting children play without parental supervision (6). Behaviour (Knowledge, Attitude, Practice) and the family environment have a big enough role in building the child's personality because the family is the first thing the child knows in this world. Children often imitate all the behaviour they see, especially in the family environment because it is in the family that children first know education as a whole (7).

Parenting in a family full of love and education about the values of life, society, and religion that is given is a conducive factor to preparing children to become healthy individuals and members of society (From Psychological Factors) (8) (9). According to Yusuf (2018), what is meant by parenting is the way, form or strategy in family education carried out by parents. The pattern of giving love from parents plays an important role in providing a standard of behaviour and a source of motivation for children to comply with this regulation (10).

Some factors like hygiene, sanitation, provision of clean water sources, family toilets, the provision of clean water sources, and the behaviour of washing hands with soap are causes of health problems (11). Knowledge and skills that must be mastered by mothers in providing nutritious food for children include the selection of food ingredients, processing and serving of food. Various good habits include feeding (time/meal schedule, meal portion and food quality) small children aged above 6 months with a variety of food in small portions every day in addition to breast milk (BM), active feeding, feeding during illness, and healing and dealing with children who have low appetite (12).

Habits of Cleaning the body, food and the environment plays an important role in maintaining health and preventing diarrheal diseases and worm infections. A clean habit, such as washing hands with soap before eating and after defecating, has become the focus of a WHO campaign to reduce the incidence of diarrheal diseases. A habit to obtain the health service in addition to provide complete immunization to the infant before his first birthday, medical treatment to the childhood and getting professional help at the right time are very important in maintaining the health of children (13). Some of the advantages of the positive deviance approach provide a solution that can solve the problem immediately.

- 1) Reachable. Positive deviance can be reached and the family don't have to depend on the external sources to practice new behaviour. The implementation is cheaper and effective compared to building nutritional rehabilitation centre or carrying out the investment in the hospital;
- 2) Participative. Public participation takes important role in the whole process starting from finding out the behaviour and success strategy among the community to supporting mother and infant after the activity ended;
- 3) Sustainable. The approach of positive deviance is the sustainable approach because some new behaviours have been comprehended and sustainable after the activity ended. This activity doesn't only change the behaviour of each individual of the family, but also change people's point of view toward malnutrition and their ability to change the situation;
- 4) Original. Since the solution has been available in that place, so the progress can be immediately achieved without using more analysis and external sources. This approach can be widely applied because positive deviance actors are always present in almost every society. It is also culturally acceptable. Since this approach is based on local behavior identified in the social, ethnic, linguistic and religious contexts of each community, so the definition is appropriate to the local culture.

Based on Behavior Change, this approach does not prioritize the acquisition of knowledge, but there are three steps of the behavior change process that are included in it they are: discovery, demonstration (nutrition POS activity) and implementation (nutrition POS activity and at home). According to Supariasa et al (2020), nutritional status is an expression of a state of balance in the form of certain variables, while according to Almatsier (2021), nutritional status is the body condition as a result of food consumption and the use of nutrient. Under the Red Line (BGM) is a toddler whose weight is weighed on the red line or below the red line on the KMS (14).

Table 1. Classification of Nutritional Status of Children Under Five Years (Toddler).

Indicator	Nutritional Status	Threshold
Body weight based on the age (BW/A), to examine the age status and it is chronic	More nutrition Good nutrition	>2SD =2SD until =-2SD

dealing with the community health	Less nutrition Worst nutrition	<-2SD until =-3SD <-3SD
Body height based on the age (BH/A), to measure the change in the past	Normal Stunted	>2SD <-2SD
Body weight based on body height (BW/BH), to examine the current nutrition	Fat Normal Wasted Very Thin	>2SD =-2SD sampai 2SD <2SD sampai =-3SD <-3SD

Nutrition is one of the necessities of human life which is closely related to the physical and mental quality of human. The state of nutrition includes the process of providing and using nutrients for growth, development, maintenance and activity (15). The state of malnutrition can occur due to an imbalance in the intake of nutrient, digestive disease factors, absorption and infectious disease. Unbalanced nutrition can cause various health problems, including:

Kwashiorkor

The definition of kwashiorkor is a form of malnutrition caused by a severe protein deficiency that can be caused by insufficient consumption of energy and calories by the body. Kwashiorkor or starvation is a syndrome of a disorder known as Protein Energy Malnutrition (MEP) with several characteristics such as edema and growth failure, depigmentation, hyperkeratosis (8).

The clinical symptoms of rekwashiorkor include generalized edema, especially on the backs of the feet (dorsum pedis), rounded and puffy face, droopy eyes, thin reddish hair like corn silk and easy to pull out without pain and loss, changes in mental status, apathy and fussiness, changes in mood, muscle shrinkage, skin disorders in the form of pink patches that expand and change color to blackish brown and peeling, and often accompanied by acute illness, anemia and diarrhea.

Marasmus

Marasmus is one of the most common form of malnutrition in toddlers. The causes of which are very low food intake, infection, birth defect, prematurity, neonatal disease and environmental health. The clinical symptom of maramus includes the body looks very thin, the face looks like an old man, whiny, fussy, wrinkled skin, very little subcutaneous tissue, often accompanied by chronic infectious disease and diarrhea or difficulty urinating.

Marasmik-Kwashiorkor

The clinical symptom of marasmic-kwashiorkor include a combination of clinical symptom between kwashiorkor and marasmus, with B/W. There are 3 indirect causes of malnutrition, namely:

1. Insufficient family food security. Each family is expected to be able to meet the food needs of all family members with good nutrition;
2. The pattern of parenting affects the nutritional condition of the children, because the children who are cared for by their own mothers with love will get better nutrition than children who are cared for by other people. Every family and community are expected to provide time, attention, and support for children so that they can grow and develop well physically, mentally and socially;
3. Improper health service and environment.

The three factors are related to family education, knowledge and skill. The higher the level of education, knowledge and skills, the more families use health services. However, if the level of education, knowledge and skills of the family is very low, it can be ascertained that the family's economic level is also low, thus it affects the level of family food security which is also low and the use of health service is less, which will eventually lead to various health problems in the family, including cases of malnutrition.

1) The impact of malnutrition toward children under five years

Malnutrition is one of the main nutritional problems in Indonesian children under five years old. Malnutrition (problems) in children under five can cause marasmus, kwashiorkor or marasmik-kwashiorkor which will also cause growth disorders in school-age children. This disorder will become serious if not treated intensively. Positive Behavior/Hearth Specialist Programs usually have the following ultimate goals:

- 2) Children with malnutrition get rehabilitation;
- 3) Families can maintain their children's nutritional rehabilitation outcomes independently at home and prevent malnutrition among children in society, both now and in the future.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Corona Virus

Corona virus diseases 2019 or what we usually call covid-19 is currently a problem in Indonesia and even in the world. This can bring new changes to the social order of Indonesian people's lives. The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends programs to reduce the case rate of Covid-19 transmission (1). The importance of a mother's role is primarily evident from the birth of her child (2). In order that the pattern of nutritional intake of pregnant women to be in accordance with health standards, besides having to manage the right diet, it is also important to regulate the right parenting as well (3). The right parenting can be done by giving full attention and affection to the child and giving enough time to the child to enjoy togetherness with all family members (4). Nutritional intake patterns play an important role in providing nutritional intake standards (Needs: Carbohydrates, Proteins, Vitamins, Minerals, Fats) that have nutritional values and standards to become balanced nutrition that

can change behaviour and provide a source of motivation for mothers to fulfil nutritional intake that can be a source of the health for pregnant women (2) (5).

The Main Cause of the Death of Children Under Five

The main cause of the death of children under five, during the pregnancy, in developing countries, deal with malnutrition is 35%, pneumonia is 20%, diarrhea is 15%, malaria is 11%, perinatal is 23%, other is 22%, meals is 5% and HIV/AIDS. Mother's behavior regarding parenting pattern, feeding pattern, hygiene pattern and habit of bringing to health services and early life nutrition are expected to overcome bad behavior such as letting children play without parental supervision (6). Behaviour (Knowledge, Attitude, Practice) and the family environment have a big enough role in building the child's personality because the family is the first thing the child knows in this world. Children often imitate all the behaviour they see, especially in the family environment because it is in the family that children first know education as a whole (7).

METHODS

This research uses qualitative methods by creating and observing works, books, academic research, videos, internet sources, and people's habits. This research tries to show the causes of under-five deaths and how to solve the problem.

RESULTS AND DISSCUSIONS

Based on the result of the research on the nutritional status of children under five in Baregbeg Village, Baregbeg District, Ciamis Regency in 2021, the largest frequency is 43 people (58.1%) which is included in the category of undernourished. Nutrition is one of the necessities of human life which is closely related to the physical and the mental quality of a human. The state of nutrition includes the process of providing and using nutrients for growth, development, maintenance and activity (16).

Malnutrition can occur due to imbalance in nutrient intake, digestive disease factors, absorption and infectious diseases. Nutritional problems are very complex and they have very broad dimension, not only concerning health aspects but also social, economic, cultural problems, parenting, education, environment, and behavior. Considering that the causes are very complex, the management of malnutrition requires comprehensive cooperation from all parties, not only medical staff, but also parents, families, religious leaders and the government.

The result of this research is in line with the opinion of the Food and Nutrition Information Network (2015) which states that malnutrition is one of the main nutritional problems in Indonesian children under five (17). Malnutrition (problems) in children under five can cause marasmus, kwashiorkor or miasmic-kwashiorkor which will also cause growth disorders in school-age children. This disorder will become serious if not treated intensively. The habit of feeding small children aged over 6 months with a variety of food in

small portions every day, active feeding, feeding during illness and healing and dealing with children who have low appetite that reflects the interaction of mothers with children will be positively related with the nutritional status of children (18). This means that children aged 0-5 years with bad nutritional status reflects that the family has bad feeding habit.

Food intake is a direct cause of the nutritional status of children under five, in addition to an infectious disease. Families are not good at providing food to children under five years of age can be caused in the limited provision of food with full of nutrients (2). Another cause is the busy mother or other caregivers in earning a living such as working in the fields so that there is less time in terms of good feeding and lack of time to prepare a complete meal. In addition, the poor nutritional status may be caused by infectious diseases in children under five. Infectious diseases can occur in children due to lack of food intake which can cause low body resistance, making them susceptible to infection. Parenting Habits. Good and correct parenting, including giving attention, can create normal child development. This means that children aged 0-5 years who have poor nutritional status have the opportunity in families to apply bad parenting habits compared to children in families with good parenting patterns. So a good parenting pattern, including paying attention to food needs and maintaining children's health affect their nutritional status. It should be noted that in terms of the child care, the mother is the most involved person, so that it has a very large influence on the child's development (19).

To suppress the increase in Covid-19 cases, various preventive measures must absolutely be implemented, both by the government and the community. So far, preventive efforts are the best practice to reduce the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic, considering that there is no treatment that is considered effective against the SARS-CoV-2 virus. Currently, the best preventive effort is to avoid exposure to viruses based on CHLB (Clean and Healthy Living Behavior) (20). To achieve this goal, the main steps that the community wants to take are using of masks; covering mouth and nose when sneezing or coughing; washing hands regularly with soap or disinfection with hand sanitizer containing at least 60% alcohol; avoiding contact with infected people; keeping your distance from people; and refraining from touching the eyes, nose, and mouth with unwashed hands. Actual knowledge and action from the government and the public regarding PHBS will always be able to reduce the number of Covid-19 cases, so that the Covid-19 pandemic period can end quickly. Therefore, the Covid-19 pandemic can be used as a basis for compiling various programs to get free from the Covid-19 pandemic (21).

Due to limited facilities, nurses are expected to improve health services, by finding out more effective ways of conveying information or counseling by conducting Communication, Education, Information and Motivation (KEIM) to the community so that information can be spread to all levels of society through more media which are easily understood by the public, for example through social media (Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram) banners that are easier to understand (22). The Millennium Development Goal (MDG'S) is the plan for 2021 dealing with nutrition problems which are still the focus of health

problems in fulfilling nutrition for babies under five, in particular. One of the efforts to improve the nutritional status of the community is improving community nutrition services through community nutrition development, namely through the Nutrition Health program. The community needs time to the adjustment or transition to implement a change in life patterns.

However, the most important thing is not to cause harm to yourself or others. Small mistakes from our behavior in the midst of a pandemic can cause big things and even be very dangerous. Therefore, a culture of reminding each other and building a habit of discipline with one another must be carried out. In addition, self-discipline is controlling disciplinary behavior by implementing government efforts together with elements of society, ensuring the adequacy of supporting factors, such as social assistance and medical assistance for residents affected by Covid-19. The Covid-19 health protocol is a form of certainty for the nation's future sustainability. So that it is the responsibility of each individual to participate in the success of the Government's program.

To reduce the increase in Covid-19 cases, various preventive measures have been implemented, both by the government and the community. Preventive efforts are the best practice to reduce the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic, considering that there is no treatment which is considered effective against the SARS-CoV-2 virus. Preventive efforts are carried out by avoiding exposure to viruses based on CHLB (Clean and Healthy Living Behavior). To achieve this goal, the main steps that the community takes are the use of masks; cover mouth and nose when sneezing or coughing; washing hands regularly with soap or disinfection with hand sanitizer containing at least 60% alcohol; avoiding contact with infected people; keeping your distance from people; and refraining from touching the eyes, nose, and mouth with unwashed hands. Actual knowledge and action from the government and the public regarding CHLB will always be able to reduce the number of Covid-19 cases, so that the Covid-19 pandemic period can end rapidly.

Therefore, Covid-19 pandemic can be used as a basis for compiling various programs to get free from the Covid-19 pandemic. Health workers (Public Health, Nurses, Midwives) are expected to improve health services by finding out more efficient and effective ways effective in conveying information or counseling by conducting Communication, Education, Information and Motivation (KEIM) to the public so that information can be spread to all levels of society through media that are easier to understand by the public.

CONCLUSIONS

Nutritional intake pattern plays an important role in providing standard nutritional intake (Needs: Carbohydrates, Proteins, Vitamins, Minerals, Fats). In the Covid-19 pandemic. All citizens must be disciplined in complying with government regulations, policies and appeals in order to break the chain of the spread of Covid-19. The government, community members, private parties, religious institutions, community leaders work hand in hand, help each other, support, remind each other together against Covid-19. Information sources are additional knowledge insights for health science about public knowledge and

compliance in implementing health protocols for the sake of Indonesia creating a strong, big, advanced and healthy nation. Keep my country, my motherland in victory.

FURTHER STUDY

This research aims to pay attention to the efforts of mothers to pay attention to the nutritional status of toddlers 0-5 years on the need for nutritional intake in early life during the growth and development period, so that pregnant women can prepare for nutritional needs during their pregnancy (from carbohydrates, protein, fat, vitamins, minerals). during the Covid-19 period by utilizing local wisdom in the Ciamis area, sources of these nutrients such as carbohydrates (cassava, taro, corn, potatoes, cassava), protein (bebeong/eel fish, catfish, carp, eel, eggs, tempeh), fat (Goat's milk/the like), Vitamins (Guava, Banana, Tomato, Mangosteen, Lobby, Jackfruit, Sapodilla, Orange, Bencoy etc.), Minerals (Pure Water, Young Coconut Water, Nira) / these things that can be consumed by the community while preserving local wisdom and culture which is still upheld. Nutritional needs throughout the life cycle are very important, where these nutrients can help pregnant women to meet their nutritional needs. This is in line with and supports the Pro government gram on stunting.

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The author hopes that the results of this research can be useful.

Declarations

Contribution in this research regarding the Tridarma of Lecturers, in the field of Health sciences providing efforts to Women During the Life Cycle, Nutritional Needs, Growth and Development of Babies 0-5 years during the Covid-19 pandemic with Nutrition status. Efforts that are expected to become the Golden Generation are encouraged by the government, especially in the health sector. Collaboration carried out by the author and the team in an effort to increase the number of health degrees through promotive, preventive

regarding health promotion, which in this case is for pregnant women related to culture, conservation by preserving local wisdom in the Ciamis area.

Author Contribution

ASM carried out the study conception and grand design of this research.
TR and NR carried out the data collection
ASM, TR, DAW carried out the data analysis and interpretation of results
NR, TS carried out the draft manuscript preparation
TS, ASM carried out of the reviewed the result

REFERENCES

- World Health Organization. Estimating mortality from COVID-19: Scientific brief. 2020.
- Diana R, Rachmayanti RD, Anwar F, Khomsan A, Christianti DF, Kusuma R. Food taboos and suggestions among Madurese pregnant women: a qualitative study. *J Ethn Foods*. 2018;5(4):246–53.
- Milah AS. *Nutrisi Ibu Dan Anak: Gizi Untuk Keluarga*. Edu Publisher; 2019.
- Milah AS. HUBUNGAN PENGETAHUAN IBU PENTINGNYA PEMBERIAN MAKANAN PENDAMPING ASI DENGAN ANGKA KEJADIAN STUNTING UNTUK BALITA PADA MASA PANDEMIC COVID-19 DI DESA PASIRBATANG KECAMATAN MANONJAYA KABUPATEN TASIKMALAYA TAHUN 2021. *J Innov Res Knowl*. 2022;1(8):675–82.
- Aldika Akbar MI, Mayang Sari I, Aditiawarman, Dachlan EG, Dekker G. Clinical characteristics of acute fatty liver of pregnancy in a tertiary Indonesian hospital. *J Matern Neonatal Med*. 2019;32(5):826–32.
- Laksono AD, Paramita A, Wulandari RD. Socioeconomic disparities of facility-based childbirth in Indonesia. *INA-Rxiv*; 2019.
- Ninawati M. Development of sex education books for elementary school students. *J INDRIA (Jurnal Ilm Pendidik Prasekolah dan Sekol Awal)*. 2018;3(3).
- Kartika V, Prihartini S, Syafrudin S, Jahari AB. Pola Pemberian Makan Anak (6-18 Bulan) Dan Hubungannya Dengan Pertumbuhan Dan Perkembangan Anak Pada Keluarga Miskin Dan Tidak Miskin. *Penelit gizi dan makanan*. 2012;
- Hadi A. Perkembangan dan Konsep Dasar Manajemen Humas dalam Dunia Pendidikan: Tinjauan Historis. *At-Ta'lim J Pendidik*. 2018;4(2):67–84.
- Nasir A, Yusuf A, Listiawan MY, Makhfudli M. The life experience of leprosy families in maintaining interaction patterns in the family to support healing in leprosy patients in Indonesian society. A phenomenological qualitative study. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*. 2022;16(4):e0010264.
- Sari IIK, Sulistyowati M. ANALISIS PROMOSI KESEHATAN DI PUSKESMAS KALIJUDAN TERHADAP PHBS RUMAH TANGGA IBU HAMIL. *J PROMKES*. 2018 Sep;3(2):159.
- Nugraheni G, Sulistyarini A, Zairina E. Beliefs about medicines in pregnancy: a survey using the beliefs about medicines questionnaire in Indonesia. *Int J*

- Clin Pharm. 2020;42(1):57-64.
- Dini IEDIM, Adair, Linda S dan Guilkey, David K. 1997. Age Specific Determinant of Stunting in Filipion Children. *The Journal of Nutrition*. 127 (2): 314-320.
- Almatsier, S. 2002. Prinsip Dasar Ilmu Gizi. Jakarta: PT Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- J Lampung Univ. 2(4):88-99.
- Erik E. Stunting Pada Anak Usia Dini. *Etos*. 2020;2(1):328005.
- Putri NK, Laksono AD. Predictors of childbirth services in Indonesia. *Int J Public Health*. 2022;11(2):566-73.
- Rachmah Q, Mahmudiono T, Loh SP. Predictor of Obese Mothers and Stunted Children in the Same Roof: A Population-Based Study in the Urban Poor Setting Indonesia. *Front Nutr*. 2021;8.
- Lestari EP, Madjid A, Nasution A. Faktor-Faktor yang Mempengaruhi Layanan Promosi Kesehatan pada Pasien Tuberkulosis Paru di Ruang Eboni Lantai 3 RS PMI Bogor Tahun 2017. *PROMOTOR*. 2018;1(1).
- Baliwati YF, Khomsan A, MetiDwiriani C. Pengantar pangan dan gizi. 2004;
- Ani Sukarsih PSPS. MODAL SOSIAL IBU HAMIL DALAM PROGRAM PENDAMPINGAN KADER. *J Promkes*. 2016;4(1):1-10.
- Kemenkes RI. Pedoman Pencegahan dan Pengendalian COVID-19. Jakarta: Kementerian Kesehatan RI; 2020. 0-115 p.
- Pangaribuan MT, Munandar AI. Kebijakan Pemerintah DKI Jakarta Menangani Pandemi Covid-19. *Gov J Ilmu Pemerintah*. 2021;14(1):1-9.
- Heavey E. Statistik keperawatan pendekatan praktik. 2014;